

NUTRITIVE EVALUATION OF ENSILED CASSAVA (*Manihot esculentus*, Crantz) TOPS AND GUINEA GRASS MIXTURES

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ABSTRACT

Cassava (*Manihot esculenta*, Crantz) is an all season crop grown as food for human in several parts of Nigeria, suggesting abundant of its leaf as crop residue. These leaves can be used as feed for livestock and preserved either by ensiling or drying. Cassava tops was ensiled with Guinea grass and four energy additive(cassava chips, Sorghum, millet grains and sugar) into five treatments -: treatments A (30% Cassava tops + 60% Guinea grass +10 % cassava chips), B (30 % Cassava tops + 60% Guinea grass+10 % Sorghum), C (30 % Cassava tops + 60% Guinea grass+ 10% millet grains, D (30 % Cassava tops + 60% Guinea grass+ 10 % sugar) and E (40 % Cassava tops + 60% Guinea grass + 0% additive) for 42days. Silage quality and chemical composition were determined and the acceptability to livestock was assessed in 6 West African Dwarf (WAD) goats .The colour of the silage was olive green with pH ranging from 4.3- 5.1. The acceptability of the silage was similar except for treatment D and E.

KEYWORDS: Cassava, livestock, grasses and legumes, dairy or beef production, silage additives

INTRODUCTION

Throughout the year, a major constraint facing livestock farmers in the tropics is meeting the nutritional needs of ruminants, due to the seasonality of forages. Conservation through ensilage of forage produced during the rainy season is likely to be the practice adopted by most small holder livestock owners, particularly those in dairy or beef production. However, tropical grasses and legumes are not natural ensilage material, largely because at cutting, they have a low content of water soluble carbohydrates, which are essential to successful ensilage (McDonald *et al.*, 1991). This results in them having a higher buffering capacity and the protein being susceptible to proteolysis (Woolford, 1984; McDonald *et al.*, 1991). However, the levels of fermentable carbohydrates can be improved through various treatments including using silage additives.

Cassava tops, a waste product of cassava plant farming has little or no economic value as over 90 % of the leaves are often left on the field to decay after cassava tuber harvest. Presently its use in human and livestock diet is relatively low, even though it is a valuable feed resource for livestock due to their high protein content. It contains quite high crude protein up to 25 % on dry matter (DM) basis (Adewusi and Bradbury, 1993, Ravindran, 1991), a nutrient which is generally deficient in feeds for livestock in the tropics. Collection of leaves after root harvest could solve one of the farmers' problems of feed shortages particularly in the dry season, and to improve feed quality. Preservation of the excess in form of silage will maximize and improve its efficiency as feed as it can be stored and utilized for a longer period of time as a protein feed supplement. Silage additives, however should be added to ensure successful fermentation when the ensiled material, such as cassava tops which has a high content of nitrogen and low concentration of water soluble carbohydrates (Petersson, 1988).

However, feeding such high protein forage as a single feed to ruminants is not an efficient feeding practice. Hence the need to consider the effects of ensiling in mixture with grasses such as Guinea grass (*Panicum maximum*). The present study was designed to evaluate the qualitative characteristics, chemical composition of ensiled cassava tops and Guinea grass mixture with different additives

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The experiment was carried out at the Small ruminant unit of the Teaching and Research Farm, University of Ibadan, Nigeria. Cassava tops were collected at post-harvest from commercial farms around Ibadan, chopped and wilted for 12 h over night. Two months regrowth of Guinea grass was used. It was also chopped and wilted over night. Four energy additives were used which include; cassava chips, Sorghum grain, Millet and sugar. All the grains were crushed before use. The ensilage was done in five treatments: A (30% Cassava tops + 60%

Guinea grass +10 % cassava chips), B (30 % Cassava tops + 60 % Guinea grass+10 % Sorghum); C (30 % Cassava tops + 60% Guinea grass+ 10% millet grains); D (30 % Cassava tops + 60% Guinea grass+ 10 % sugar) and E (40 % Cassava tops + 60% Guinea grass + 0% additive). Silage materials were filled in layer by layer, compacted, sealed up and compressed with 'sand-bag'. Fermentation was done for 42 days. The pH, colour, smell and texture were determined (Babayemi *et al.*, 2009).

A representative sample of fresh cassava top and Guinea grass were taken for dry matter determination and other analysis. Data were analysed using analysis of variance (SAS, 1995). Significant means were separated using the Duncan (1955) multiple range F-test.

Acceptability study

Six West African dwarf goats weighing 10 – 12 kg and about two years old were used to evaluate the free choice intake of ensiled cassava tops with *Panicum maximum*, (Guinea grass). In triplicates, 1 kg each of the ensiled cassava tops and Guinea grass were placed in strategic locations in plastic feeding troughs. The goats were allowed to feed for 6 hours daily and for upward of 7 days. Consumption was measured by deduction of remnants from the amount of feed served. The forage preferred was assessed from the coefficient of preference (COP) value, calculated from the ratio between the intakes for the individual forages, divided by the average intake of the forages (Babayemi *et al.*, 2006a). Therefore, silage was inferred to be relatively acceptable provided the COP was greater than unity.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 shows the colour, odour, texture, smell, pH and temperature of ensiled cassava tops and Guinea grass mixture. The colour was observed to be the same in all the silages. The colours were close to the original colour of both the grass and cassava foliage and this was slightly different from the finding of Oduguwa *et al.* (2007). The pH obtained ranged from 4.3 to 5.1 the lowest being in treatment B and the highest in treatment D.

These were however higher than those of Oduguwa *et al.* (2007). Additives are used to improve silage preservation by ensuring that lactic acid bacteria dominate the fermentation phase. Possibly the most important benefit of additives such as maize or sorghum grain or cassava meal is to improve DM in early-cut crops when moisture content is high and where effluent is lost to the silage through seepage. Tropical grasses have been successfully ensiled when supplemented with maize meal (Van Onselen and Lopez, 1988), cassava meal (Panditharane *et al.*, 1986) and sorghum grain (Alberto *et al.*, 1993).

Table 2 presents the chemical composition of ensiled cassava tops and Guinea grass mixture. Crude protein and crude fibre of the silage with the different additives ranged from 20.56 to 24.15 % and 31.11 to 32.90% respectively. NDF was highest in treatment 'C' (76.41 %) while ADF was highest in treatment B (24.95%) and Lowest (21.11 %) was recorded in Treatment "C". The NDF reported was higher than results from Oduguwa *et al.* (2007), but ADF was in the range reported.

Presented in Table 3 is the acceptability of the ensiled cassava tops and Guinea grass mixture that the goats had free choice on. Based on their COP values of more than unity, Treatment A, B and C were preferred compared to Treatment D and E.

CONCLUSION

Cassava tops and Guinea grass silage thus has the potential to serve as a protein bank to correct nutrient deficiency, especially during the dry season where most of ruminant livestock are fed low protein diets based predominantly on crop-residues and native grass.

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Table 1: Effects of additives on quality of ensiled cassava tops with Guinea grass

Treatment	Silage quality						
	Colour	Smell	Texture	pH	Moisture	Temperature (° C)	Other observation
60 % GG + 30 % CF+ 10% cassava chips	Olive green	Fruity	Firm	5.0	71.19	29	Mouldy at the top side
60 % GG + 30 % CF+ 10% Sorghum grain	Olive green	Fruity	Firm	4.3	72.95	29	Mouldy at the top
60 % GG + 30 % CF+ 10% millet grain	Olive green	Fruity	Firm	4.9	71.18	28.5	None
60 % GG + 30 % CF+ 10% sugar	Olive green	Fruity	Firm	5.1	72.55	29	None
60 % GG + 40 % CF+ 0% additive	Olive green	Fruity	Firm	5.0	71.73	29	None

GG- Guinea grass, CT -Cassava tops

Table 2: Effects of additives on Chemical composition (%) of ensiled cassava tops and Guinea grass mixture

Treatment	DM	Crude protein	Crude fibre	Ash	NDF	ADF	Organic matter	Ether extract
60 % GG + 30 % CF+ 10% cassava chips	28.81	22.32	31.96	9.57	73.33	43.24	90.43	8.46
60 % GG + 30 % CF+ 10% Sorghum grain	27.05	22.42	32.90	8.51	71.45	45.13	91.49	8.46
60 % GG + 30 % CF+ 10% millet grain	28.82	24.15	32.07	9.54	76.41	40.57	90.46	10.38
60 % GG + 30 % CF+ 10% sugar	27.45	20.56	31.96	7.45	69.56	44.18	92.55	9.40
60 % GG + 40 % CF+ 0% additive	28.27	23.51	31.11	9.55	68.81	48.07	90.45	8.48

GG- Guinea grass, CT- Cassava tops

Table3: Coefficient of preference of ensiled cassava tops and Guinea grass mixture with different additives

Treatment	Mean daily consumption (g/DM)	Coefficient of preference (COP)
60 % GG + 30 % CF+ 10% cassava chips	906.14	1.11
60 % GG + 30 % CF+ 10% Sorghum grain	836.86	1.03
60 % GG + 30 % CF+ 10% millet grain	838.29	1.02
60 % GG + 30 % CF+ 10% sugar	730.43	0.90
60 % GG + 40 % CF+ 0% additive	757.57	0.89

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